

Stability-indicating spectrofluorimetric methods for determination of gemifloxacin mesylate in pharmaceutical dosage forms

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Abstract : Two spectrofluorimetric methods were developed for the determination of gemifloxacin mesylate (GFX) in pure and dosage forms. The native fluorescence of GFX allow the determination of 0.05–2.25 µg/mL of this drug in aqueous solution containing borate buffer (pH 8), with $\lambda_{\text{exc}} = 272$ nm and $\lambda_{\text{em}} = 400$ nm. Micelle-enhanced fluorescence led to 700% higher analytical signals in presence of sodium dodecyl sulphate (pH 9), which allow the determination of 0.001–0.12 µg/mL GFX with $\lambda_{\text{exc}} = 272$ nm and $\lambda_{\text{em}} = 400$ nm. Both methods were successfully applied to GFX determination in pharmaceutical preparations. The methods were extended to stability study of GFX. The drug was exposed to acidic, alkaline, oxidative and photolytic degradation according to ICH guidelines. The rate of GFX degradation was found at its highest in acidic condition, and in its lowest in the neutral one. It was, however, found to be stable under dry heat and photolytic degradation conditions.

Keywords : Gemifloxacin mesylate (GFX), spectrofluorimetry, pharmaceutical preparations, stability-indicating.

Introduction

Gemifloxacin (GFX) (Fig. 1) is a fourth generation synthetic broad-spectrum fluorinated quinolone antibacterial agent for oral administration¹. It is present in two forms; either as free GFX base or as GFX mesylate salt. GFX has a broad-spectrum activity against both Gram-negative and Gram-positive microorganisms^{2–5}. The main advantages of GFX over the older agents of fluoroquinolones is retaining the excellent activity against Gram-negative bacilli and improving Gram-positive activity (including *S. pneumoniae* and *Staphylococcus aureus*)^{6,7}. Therefore, GFX was approved by the Food and Drug Administration (FDA) in April 2003 for treatment of acute bacterial exacerbation of chronic bronchitis, mild-to-mod-

erate pneumonia multidrug resistant *S. pneumoniae* as well as community-acquired pneumonia^{7–9}.

The published methods for the determination of GFX included high-performance liquid chromatography^{10–18}, high-performance liquid chromatography-tandem mass spectrometry (LC-MS-MS)^{19,20}, voltammetry²¹, potentiometry²², capillary electrophoresis^{23,24}, spectrophotometry^{25–31}, chemiluminescence³² and spectrofluorimetry³³.

Spectrofluorimetry has been widely used in the determination of pharmaceutical compounds because it is highly sensitive, selective, easily operated and economical technique. The main goal of the present study was to investigate the native fluorescence characteristics of GFX in aqueous medium and in SDS micellar medium. The proposed method was fully validated according to ICH guidelines, and successfully applied for the determination of the drug tablets and was extended to establish the inherent stability of GFX under different stress conditions such as : alkaline, acidic, oxidative and photolytic conditions. The proposed method has wide linear dynamic range and is more sensitive than reported fluorimetric methods³³.

Fig. 1. Structure of GFX.

The stability of the active substance and/or finished product is essential for safe delivery of the therapeutic purposes. The presence of potential degradation products may cause transformation of chemical, pharmacological, and/or toxicological properties of the active drug^{34,35}. Pharmaceuticals are sensitive to environmental variables such as temperature, humidity, and light. These factors usually vary during manufacturing, transportation, storage, and distribution of the finished product. As a result, stability testing of the active substance and the finished product is vital for providing information about potential degradation products, possible degradation pathways of the drug, compatibility of the drug with the excipients in the finished product, and the long-term effects of the environmental factors on the active drug and its finished products. Results of stability testing are important in developing proper manufacturing process; selecting proper packaging, storage conditions, product's shelf life; and determining the expiration date^{36,37}.

In the assay published for gemifloxacin, chromatographic profiles are included for acidic, basic, and neutral stress conditions as well as oxidative stress conditions. A total of eight different degradation products were found with the greatest number and amounts of them produced under acidic conditions. However, none of the impurities were identified in the study³⁸. These techniques are accurate and sensitive but time-consuming, expensive, and greatly rely on laboratory facilities as well as experimental skills³⁹.

The proposed method can be considered as a simple and fast alternative to the already existing stability indicating HPLC procedure¹⁴.

During the review and publication processes of this study, a paper on the spectrofluorimetric determination of GFX appeared using a similar procedure⁴⁰. However, the method used in the present study has proven to be more sensitive. While the linearity range in the above mentioned study was 10–1000 ng/mL, our method gave readings in the range of 1–120 ng/mL. This notable difference in sensitivity can be traced to our conscious decision of using basic buffer as opposed to acidic buffer used in other study.

Also, the paper did not deal with the determination of drug with the stability study of the drug. Since the pur-

pose of stability studies is to monitor possible changes to a product or a material over a time at different storage conditions, it is expected that, only those methods that are stability indicating should be used.

Experimental

Apparatus :

The fluorescence intensity was measured on a Perkin-Elmer model LS-55 luminescence spectrometer (UK), equipped with a 150W xenon arc lamp, grating excitation and emission monochromators and a Perkin-Elmer recorder. Slit widths for excitation and emission monochromators were set at 5.0 and 7.0 nm, respectively. A 1-cm quartz cell was used. pH was measured on a HANNA pH meter (Romania).

Materials and reagents :

All reagents used were of analytical reagent grade, and distilled water was used throughout the study : GFX mesylate was kindly supplied from Saudi Pharmaceutical Industries and Medical Appliances Corporation, Al-Qassim Pharmaceutical Plant (SPIMACO), Saudi Arabia. (Factive® 320 mg/tablet) was provided by (SPIMACO), Saudi Arabia. Sodium dodecyl sulfate (SDS, 95.0%) (Winlab, UK), 1.0% aqueous solution was prepared. Sodium hydroxide (0.2 mol/L solution), boric acid (0.2 mol/L solution) (BDH, UK). Borate buffer solutions (0.2 mol/L), covering the pH range of 6.5–9.5, were prepared by mixing appropriate volumes of 0.2 mol/L boric acid and 0.2 mol/L NaOH and adjusting the pH using a pH meter.

Stock and standard solutions : Stock solution of GFX was prepared by dissolving 10.0 mg of the drug in 100 mL of distilled water. This solution was further diluted with the same solvent to obtain a working solution containing 5 µg/mL of GFX. The solutions were stable for 2 weeks when kept in the refrigerator and protected from light.

General procedure :

Procedure for calibration graphs :

For aqueous-solution fluorimetric method : Aliquots of working solutions GFX, were pipetted in 10-ml calibrated flasks and diluted to the mark with borate buffer (pH 8). Final GFX concentrations were over the range of 0.05–2.25 mol/L. The fluorescence emission at 400 nm was measured, using an excitation wavelength of 272 nm, against a blank solution.

For micelle-enhanced fluorimetric method : A similar procedure was applied. In this case, 7 mL borate buffer (pH 9) was used, and 1 mL of 1% SDS solution was added before diluting to the mark with water. Final concentrations of GFX in this case were over the range 0.001–0.12 mol/L. The fluorescence was measured at 400 nm, with an excitation wavelength of 272 nm.

Procedure for tablets : The contents of ten tablets were pulverized into fine powder. The equivalent of 10.0 mg of GFX was transferred into 100-mL volumetric flask which was sonicated for 30 min. The solution was next diluted with distilled water, shaken and filtered. The solution eventually used for working solution preparation. A procedure named “Procedure for calibration graphs” was applied. Using the calibration graph or the corresponding regression equation, the nominal content of the tablets was calculated.

Procedures for stability study :

Acidic degradation : Aliquots of GFX standard stock solution (equivalent to 1000 µg of the drug) was transferred into a small conical flask; 5 mL aliquots of 0.1 mol/L HCl was added and heated at reflux for 2 h. At the specified time, the contents of the flask were cooled, and neutralized to pH 7.5 with 0.1 mol/L NaOH. The solution was then quantitatively transferred into 100 mL volumetric flask and completed to volume with distilled water. 1.0 mL of the resulting solution was then transferred into 100 mL volumetric flask and the procedure described under “Procedure for calibration graphs” was performed.

Alkaline degradation : The alkaline treatment was applied by mixing a aliquots of GFX standard stock solution (equivalent to 1000 µg of the drug) with 0.1 mol/L NaOH (5 mL). This mixture was kept at room temperature for 1 h, and neutralized to pH 7.5 with 0.1 mol/L HCl. The solution was then quantitatively transferred into 100 mL volumetric flask and completed to volume with distilled water. 1.0 mL of the resulting solution was then transferred into 100 mL volumetric flask and the procedure described under “Procedure for calibration graphs” was performed.

Degradation under neutral conditions : One milliliter of a standard stock solution (equivalent to 1000 µg of the drug) was transferred into 100 mL volumetric flask; 5 mL of double distilled water was added and heated using

water bath for 3 h at 80 °C. The contents of the volumetric flask were cooled; and completed to volume with distilled water. One milliliter of the resulting solution was then transferred into 100 mL volumetric flask and the procedure described under “Procedure for calibration graphs” was performed.

Oxidative degradation : Aliquots of GFX standard stock solution (equivalent to 1000 µg of the drug) was transferred into a small conical flask; 5 mL aliquots of (3% v/v) H₂O₂ was added and heated at reflux for a period of 2 h. The solution was then quantitatively transferred into 100 mL volumetric flask and completed to volume with distilled water. 1.0 mL of the resulting solution was then transferred into 100 mL volumetric flask and the procedure described under “Procedure for calibration graphs” was performed.

Photo degradation : Photolytic degradation studies were also carried out by drug exposure to sunlight and UV light (254 nm) for a period of 8 and 3 h, respectively. A stock standard solution of GFX was prepared by dissolving 10.0 mg of the drug in 10 mL of distilled water. One milliliter of the resulting solution was then transferred into 100 mL volumetric flask and the procedure described under “Procedure for calibration graphs” was performed.

Dry heat studies : To study dry heat degradation, solid drug was exposed in oven at 80° for 12 h. After heating, 100 µg GFX was weighed and transferred to volumetric flask (10 ml) and diluted up to the mark with distilled water. One milliliter of the resulting solution was then transferred into 100 mL volumetric flask and the procedure described under “Procedure for calibration graphs” was performed.

Results and discussion

Fluorescence characteristics of GFX in aqueous solution :

Fig. 2 shows the excitation and emission spectra for aqueous borate buffer (pH 8.0) solution of GFX. A maximum at 272 nm can be clearly observed in the excitation spectrum, the emission spectrum shows its maximum at 400 nm. These excitation and emission wavelengths were selected for the following assays to measure the fluorescence intensity. The influence of pH in the range of 1.03–12 on the fluorescence of GFX was studied using 0.1 mol/L H₂SO₄, 0.2 mol/L acetate buffer and 0.2 mol/L

Fig. 2. Fluorescence (FL) spectra of GFX (0.1 µg/mL) : (A, B) in pH 8.0 borate buffer, (A', B') in pH 9.0 borate buffer/SDS system. Where (A, A') are the excitation spectra and (B, B') are the emission spectra.

borate buffer. Fluorescence exhibits a maximum within a pH range 7.5–8.5 as seen in Fig. 3. Thus, borate buffer of pH 8.0 was chosen for the spectrofluorimetric determination of GFX. The effect of the total borate buffer volume was also investigated by increasing the volumes of borate buffer and completing to the mark with distilled water. It was found that increasing the volumes of buffer

solution resulted in corresponding increase in fluorescence intensity. Hence, dilution of GFX should be performed strictly with borate buffer.

Fluorescence characteristics of GFX in micellar media :

The fluorescence properties of GFX in various micellar media were studied, there was an enhancement of the fluorescence intensity in presence of SDS compared with aqueous solution (about 7.0-fold enhancement), and so that SDS was used as a fluorescence enhancer in order to develop a new spectrofluorimetric method for the determination of GFX (Fig. 2).

Effect of surfactants : The fluorescence properties of GFX in various micellar media were studied using anionic surfactant (SDS), cationic surfactant (CTAB, CPC) and non-ionic surfactant (Triton® X-100, methyl cellulose). An increase in fluorescence intensity was observed only when SDS, methyl cellulose or CTAB were added. As can be seen in Fig. 4, best results were achieved with SDS solutions, so a SDS medium was employed in further studies.

Effect of the volume of SDS : The influence of SDS on the fluorescence intensity was studied using increasing volumes of 1.0% w/v SDS. It was found that increasing volumes of SDS solution resulted in a corresponding increase in fluorescence intensity up to 1.0 mL, further additions of this surfactant provoked no increment of fluorescence intensity; thus, 1 mL of 1.0% w/v SDS solution was chosen as the optimum volume for GFX (Fig. 5).

Fig. 3. pH influence on the fluorescence (FL) of GFX (0.1 µg/mL) : (A) aqueous solution and (B) 0.1% SDS micellar solution.

Fig. 4. Effect of type of surfactant (1 mL of 1.0% solution of each surfactant) on the fluorescence (FL) of GFX (0.025 µg/mL).

Fig. 5. Effect of the volume of 1.0% SDS on the fluorescence (FL) of GFX (0.1 µg/mL).

Effect of pH : The influence of pH on the micelle-enhanced fluorescence intensity was studied. As can be seen in Fig. 3, analytical signal reaches a maximum at pH 9. Thus, borate buffer of pH 9 was chosen for the micelle-enhanced spectrofluorimetric determination of GFX.

Effect of borate buffer volume : The effect of the buffer volume was also investigated using increasing volumes of borate buffer (pH 9) and completing to the mark with distilled water. Accordingly, a 7 ml aliquot of the buffer solution for 10 ml total volume was selected as a suitable volume for the recommended procedure.

Validation of the spectrofluorimetric and micelle-enhanced spectrofluorimetric determination of GFX :

Linearity : Two series of five standard solutions of GFX with concentrations between 0.001 and 2.25 mol/L

were prepared by triplicate and measured by following the procedures described in the experimental section. Table 1 resumes the calibration parameters obtained from statistical analysis of the data.

Limit of quantification (LOQ) and limit of detection (LOD) : The limit of quantification (LOQ) was determined by establishing the lowest concentration that can be measured according to ICH Q2 (R1) recommendations⁴¹ below which the calibration graph is nonlinear. The limit of detection (LOD) was determined by evaluating the lowest concentration of the analyte that can be readily detected. The results were summarized in Table 1.

LOQ and LOD were calculated according to the following equations :

$$\text{LOQ} = 10S_a/b$$

$$\text{LOD} = 3.3S_a/b$$

Table 1. Performance data for the proposed fluorimetric and micelle-enhanced fluorimetric methods

Parameter	Aqueous solution method	Micelle-enhanced method
Concentration range ($\mu\text{g/mL}$)	0.05–2.25	0.001–0.12
Intercept	68.94	179.9
Slope	414.63	6004.5
Correlation coefficient (r)	0.9999	0.9999
Limit of detection (LOD) ($\mu\text{g/mL}$)	9.5×10^{-3}	2.25×10^{-5}
Limit of quantification (LOQ) ($\mu\text{g/mL}$)	0.029	6.83×10^{-5}
Standard deviation of the intercept (S_a)	1.197	0.041
Standard deviation of the slope (S_b)	0.913	0.554

where, S_a is the standard deviation of the intercept of regression line and b is the slope of the regression line.

Accuracy and precision : Statistical analysis⁴² of the results obtained by the proposed and reported methods²⁸ using student's t -test and variance ratio F -test showed no significant differences between them regarding accuracy and precision, respectively (Table 2). The intraday precision was evaluated by determination of three concentration of GFX in pure form on three successive occasions.

The interday precision was also evaluated through replicate analysis of three concentrations for a period of 3 successive days. The results of intraday and interday precision are summarized in Table 3.

Robustness of the method. The robustness of the adopted methods was demonstrated by the constancy of the fluorescence intensity with minor changes in the experimental conditions, such as the pH 8 ± 0.2 for aqueous solution method, pH 9 ± 0.2 for micelle-enhanced method and the change in the volume of SDS ± 0.5 . These minor changes that may take place during the experimental operations did not affect the fluorescence intensity.

Results of stability studies :

Various stress conditions were tested. The results of these tests are presented in Table 4. GFX was found to be stable under dry heat and photolytic degradation conditions. Significant degradation of GFX was observed in acidic condition. 81.6% degradation of the original sample resulted after boiling for 2 h with 0.1 mol/L HCl. The rate of degradation in acid medium is more than degradation in alkaline, neutral and oxidative medium. Results were comparable to those obtained by HPLC method. The proposed method is simple, rapid and inexpensive, and thus from an economic perspective seems a good alternative to previously reported HPLC stability indicating method.

Table 2. Application of the proposed and comparison methods to the determination of GFX in pure form and its pharmaceutical dosage form

	Proposed methods		Reported method ²⁸
	Aqueous solution method	Micelle-enhanced method	
Pure form			
Mean \pm SD	99.27 \pm 0.625	99.37 \pm 0.497	99.50 \pm 0.747
N	6	6	6
%RSD	0.6296	0.500	0.7510
t -test	0.245 (2.228) ^a	0.356 (2.228) ^a	
F -test	1.427 (5.05) ^a	2.259 (5.05) ^a	
Factive® 320 mg (tablet)			
Mean \pm SD	99.58 \pm 0.512	99.57 \pm 0.524	99.38 \pm 0.387
N	6	6	6
%RSD	0.5140	0.526	0.3890
t -test	0.763 (2.228) ^a	0.714 (2.228) ^a	
F -test	1.750 (5.05) ^a	1.837 (5.05) ^a	

^aFigures in parentheses are the tabulated t and F values at confidence limits 95%⁴².

Table 3. Validation of the proposed methods for the determination of GFX in pure form

Proposed methods	Concentration ($\mu\text{g/mL}$) taken	% Recovery	% RSD	% Error
Aqueous solution method :				
Intraday precision	0.08	99.30 \pm 0.32	0.32	0.19
	1.00	99.60 \pm 0.61	0.61	0.35
	1.50	99.30 \pm 0.60	0.60	0.35
Interday precision	0.08	99.10 \pm 0.20	0.20	0.12
	1.00	99.20 \pm 0.31	0.31	0.18
	1.50	99.20 \pm 0.32	0.32	0.18
Micelle-enhanced method :				
Intraday precision	0.008	100.10 \pm 0.26	0.26	0.15
	0.050	99.60 \pm 0.20	0.20	0.08
	0.080	99.80 \pm 0.20	0.20	0.12
Interday precision	0.008	99.10 \pm 0.62	0.63	0.36
	0.050	99.00 \pm 0.40	0.40	0.23
	0.080	99.20 \pm 0.21	0.21	0.12

Table 4. Forced degradation study results

Condition	Time (h)	GFX ^a (%)	
		Aqueous solution method	Micelle-enhanced method
Acid (0.1 mol/L HCl, heated at reflux)	2	17.70	17.02
Base (0.1 mol/L NaOH, room temperature)	1	67.40	66.96
Water (80 °C)	3	84.60	84.90
Hydrogen peroxide (3%, heated at reflux)	2	62.30	62.10
Heat dry, 80 °C (solid)	12	99.90	100.30
Exposure to sunlight	8	98.30	99.40
Exposure to UV light (254 nm)	3	99.40	99.40

^aRemaining GFX (%) after exposure to stress conditions.

Conclusions

The proposed methods are simple, rapid, reproducible, economic, and highly sensitive for determination of GFX. In comparison to previously reported fluorimetric methods, the sensitivity was enhanced more. The use of SDS micellar system provides a simple means to enhance the fluorescence from GFX. The addition of 0.1% SDS gives about 7-fold increase in sensitivity and improve the limit of detection without further sample manipulation. The methods were applied for the determination of GFX in dosage forms. Also the statistical data

represent the suitability and reproducibility of the proposed methods for routine analysis in the quality control laboratories.

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